

Spatial contexts and educational inequalities in European countries

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Abstract

Despite high overall levels of educational attainment, European countries continue to face persistent inequalities in educational opportunity rooted in social origin. This article synthesizes findings from nine case-study countries in the LEARN project to examine how individual social background, educational systems, and spatial contexts jointly shape educational trajectories. Drawing on high-quality longitudinal survey and register data, the contributions analyse key educational transitions and assess the role of school, classroom, and neighbourhood composition across diverse welfare regimes and tracking structures. Across all countries, individual socioeconomic background emerges as a strong and consistent predictor of educational outcomes. Contextual effects at the school, classroom, and neighbourhood level are also evident, though generally more modest and highly contingent on institutional settings, particularly the timing and rigidity of tracking. Early selection systems substantially limit the potential for later compensatory effects. Overall, the findings highlight the importance of early interventions, institutional design, and policies addressing social and spatial segregation to reduce educational inequalities across Europe.

Keywords: social inequality, Europe, context, neighbourhoods, spatial inequality

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1. Introduction

Although Europe is one of the most highly educated regions in the world, inequality of educational opportunity remains a significant challenge. When access to relevant educational programmes, qualifications, and standards is not equally available to all students, individual educational success depends not only on ability and motivation but also on ascriptive, non-functional characteristics such as social origin. The consequence is educational inequality, which poses a serious threat to the promise of high-quality, inclusive education for all. To better understand how and why educational inequalities are produced across diverse European countries, the LEARN project seeks to analyse high-quality longitudinal data from various educational systems over Europe to generate new insights how educational inequalities unfold. In this article, we summarize research results from the nine LEARN case-study countries to provide a comprehensive overview of how educational inequality, social backgrounds, local contexts, and educational systems are interlinked.

Decades of research have clearly demonstrated that educational inequalities are largely attributable to differences

in social origin. Children from more educated, higher-status, and affluent families tend to have better educational prospects than those from disadvantaged backgrounds. This finding has proven remarkably stable over time and across different countries. More specifically, the influence of social origin can be broken down into primary and secondary effects (Boudon, 1974). Primary effects refer to differences in competences, indicating that students from advantaged families have higher competence levels and better academic performance, on average. These effects are often attributed to differences in upbringing and early support that advantaged families are better able to provide. Secondary effects, by contrast, capture differences in educational decision-making. Even when students demonstrate equivalent academic performance, they tend to achieve higher educational attainment, because socially advantaged families opt for higher-quality, more demanding educational programmes. Research has shown that students from advantaged families have higher aspirations, are less risk-averse, receive greater familial support, and are more likely to pursue higher educational degrees.

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While this pattern is consistent across countries and reflects a generalized mechanism of educational inequality, the extent to which primary and secondary effects shape final outcomes depends on the structure of the educational system, particularly on the institutionalized decision points that mark the transitions between different educational stages and organisations (Pfeffer, 2008). Every transition requires to decide between several options and thus increases the potential for secondary effects of social origin. Educational systems in Europe vary substantially across countries and offer markedly different pathways for acquiring education over the life course. One major line of distinction concerns how the central function of sorting students is structured, as this decides about the timing, number, and parameters of decision points. An aspect of sorting that has been examined extensively in previous research was the age of (first) tracking. The ‘standard result’ of this research is that early between-school tracking increases inequality in educational opportunity without positively affecting learning efficiency (Van de Werfhorst and Mijs, 2010; Bol and Van de Werfhorst, 2013; Hanushek and Wößmann, 2006; Brunello and Checchi, 2007).

However, highly formalized educational systems alone do not guarantee that identical processes operate with respect to educational inequality. Even within formally identical school tracks, significant differences in learning opportunities and outcomes between students in different neighbourhoods or schools are found. One major factor that contributes to these differences is spatial social segregation—the phenomenon that advantaged and disadvantaged social groups tend to cluster in different neighbourhoods. Since schools are nested in neighbourhoods, they often reflect their social composition, particularly when school choice is limited, e.g. when catchment areas exist. The social composition of schools can in turn trigger advantaged families to either move to another neighbourhood or send their children to more distant or private schools, a phenomenon that reinforces social segregation.

These spatial contexts—often conceptualized as compositional effects at the level of classes, schools, or neighbourhoods—have been identified for a long time as additional sources of educational inequality. The most prominent example is the Coleman report, which showed that the social composition of schools contributed to educational achievement and highlighted the costs of racial and social segregation in the U.S. Coleman et al. (1966). In this tradition, a lot of research on the effects of school and neighbourhood composition and their mechanisms has been conducted, but a lot of research stems from the U.S., a country which differs strongly from European contexts in terms of segregation as well as educational system. In European contexts, however, these effects are still not understood well. Not only are spatial effects insuf-

ficiently theorized, but the role of spatial contexts in different educational systems and their interplay with individual social background is underexplored as well. Just as educational systems vary widely across European countries, so too do spatial contexts and their effects. It remains unclear whether certain systems are better equipped to mitigate these forms of inequality and how they account for varying contextual conditions.

This significant research gap provided the impetus for a series of papers from all nine LEARN case-study countries, which aim to generate new multinational evidence based on high-quality longitudinal data on the connections between local contexts and educational opportunities. To maximize impact, each participating country focused on major transition points within its educational system, as these are assumed to amplify secondary effects by shaping subsequent educational trajectories. This focus is particularly relevant because, although secondary effects operate continuously, they become most visible when high-stake educational decisions are made.

2. Conceptual considerations

To understand how local contexts influence individual educational success, a wide range of theoretical approaches has been developed. In this section we provide a short overview of the most relevant explanatory frameworks. As most of the empirical contributions from the nine case studies focus on school or classroom contexts, we begin by examining theories that adopt a similar perspective. We then extend the view to theories that go beyond educational contexts and consider neighbourhoods and the spatial contexts of students’ residences. Finally, it is important to understand how these nested contexts interact with each other and how segregation of individuals into different areas or quarters can be explained.

Differences in the composition of learning groups, such as school classes, might contribute directly or indirectly to skill development via educational goals, norms, motivation, and classroom discipline. Contagion theories focus on the latter, attempting to explain why some contexts are beneficial and others harmful to all students in a classroom (Jencks and Mayer, 1990). Just as germs, ideals, norms, and values can spread through a social network via interactions and create shared belief systems that influence all students in a classroom. These values can be positive representing aspects such as hard work, effort, and motivation to achieve one’s goals, they can also be negative, such as fostering slacking and delinquency. Which values will be predominant in a classroom is mostly due to the values and norms students have internalized in their homes, which depends on their social (and ethnic) background. Influential sociological explanatory frameworks, such as the Wisconsin model of status

attainment (Sewell et al., 2003), make similar assumptions. This model outlines that educational norms, values and aspirations are transmitted via interaction from significant others, such as parents, teachers, friends, and peers, to children, who then internalise these values and act accordingly. These theories are valuable because they do not only explain why social networks in given contexts can have positive or negative effects based on their predominant values, but also how these values originate (in the families of origin). Thus, a classroom is never an isolated context, but is tightly interrelated with the spatial context around it, such as the school and neighbourhood.

Apart from transmission, spillover effects may also contribute to effects of social classroom composition. For instance, advantaged families may positively influence the entire schooling environment by investing more in their children's education. Similarly, students may profit from information advantages since high-status families tend to exchange information about educational success and opportunities within their community. Finally, the social composition of the classroom may indirectly affect instructional quality through teachers' self-selection into socially advantaged and disadvantaged schools.

Students' skill development is expected to depend more directly on the ability composition of the class. Peer ability composition can influence students in the same learning group in both positive and negative ways. For instance, a mediocre student in a class of high-achieving students may, on the one hand, benefit from peers' additional support (Opdenakker et al., 2002) and more demanding teaching (Gamoran, 1986). Conversely, they may suffer from comparisons with others when it comes to grading, a classic example of the frog-pond effect, which assumes that a student's self-concept depends not only on their absolute performance, but also on their relative standing in the reference group Marsh (1987).

Although these theories put the focus on the individual, they can help us to understand how interactions between individuals work to create larger social contexts and networks. However, they also demonstrate that similar contexts can have contrasting effects via different mechanisms, posing significant challenges for empirical identification. Furthermore, the aforementioned theories were mostly tested by using average levels of students' social backgrounds or ability composition. However, it is also plausible to assume that the homogeneity or heterogeneity of a context may either facilitate or hinder learning and attitudinal change. For example, advocates of educational tracking typically argue that sorting by ability and thus generating homogeneous learning groups increases learning efficiency. Often, theoretical assumptions about averages and distributions of contexts are not clearly differentiated from each other.

The theoretical approaches mentioned so far focus on the school and classroom context, which is particularly relevant for understanding educational inequalities. As previously mentioned, the school composition often depends on neighbourhood context, but their social and ethnic composition is not always identical. Schools may serve different neighbourhoods or attract high-status families even when situated in disadvantaged areas, due to additional funding. Finally, significant others who might influence children and parents are not only found in schools, but also in the local community, e.g. friends, neighbours, or extended family members. Hence this aspect should not be overlooked, even if it often cannot be studied in detail.

In general, many mechanisms such as the transmission of norms and values easily extend beyond the classroom context and can also be applied to neighbourhoods. However, as Galster (2007) outlines, this is only a small part of potential neighbourhood effects. He compiled a list of 15 different mechanisms through which neighbourhoods can influence various relevant individual outcomes, such as education, health, or occupational success. Previous research has shown that peer influence, collective socialisation, market incentives, social disorder, discrimination and institutional conditions are the most important factors regarding education. Even rather different mechanisms can play a role, such as environmental factors, which can negatively affect educational opportunities via poor health Hillmert et al. (2023). However, some of these mechanisms have been shown to be particularly relevant in the US, where segregation often takes extreme forms with a strong ethnic and racial component. In Europe, segregation is usually less pronounced, with other forms being more relevant, particularly with regard to economic means Nieuwenhuis and Hooimeijer (2016).

Finally, the mechanisms explaining how neighbourhoods and classroom or school contexts interact should not be overlooked. Apparently, individuals are not randomly assigned to their homes, but selection mechanisms play a role. This means that individuals tend to self-select into neighbourhoods, according to their resources and social status. In Europe, economic means are the most relevant explanatory factor, determining whether one can afford to live in a prosperous area on the one end or is restricted to poor neighbourhoods offering a low quality of life but affordable housing. There is limited empirical evidence as to whether especially parents sort into areas that provide good educational opportunities for their children (Rich and Owens, 2023). When schools are strictly bound to catchment areas, families need to move; many parents do so even before their first child is born. When school choice is unrestricted, movement is unnecessary, but children have to travel further to reach their schools. Therefore, whether parents need to move may de-

pend on their children's stage of education. In summary, it seems that self-selection into neighbourhoods largely explains why there are homogeneous areas and contexts beyond schools and classrooms.

3. Methodological considerations

Measuring educational and neighbourhood contexts involves major challenges. The best suited data source for identifying the composition of learning environments are register data, because they contain complete and reliable information on students in either classrooms or grade levels within schools, and they usually offer a very large number of observations over longer periods of time. However, to derive composition measures, these data must contain information on students' social origin as well as valid and reliable information on their school performance. Since this information is not always available in education registers, they often have to be merged with other data.

An alternative approach is to measure school or classroom composition by aggregating individual survey data. This requires a survey sample which is based on classrooms in schools. However, for these measures to yield valid results, it is crucial to capture complete classroom contexts. This can be difficult when there is substantial nonresponse or survey attrition. If large portions of a school or class do not participate in a survey, aggregated indicators based on the remaining students may be severely biased. Consequently, indicators of social origin or ability can be misleading when specific population segments are missing—for instance, when socially disadvantaged or mediocre students are more likely to refuse participation. Measuring changes over time is often problematic in survey contexts, because complete contextual information must be available across extended periods. This requirement typically limits the usefulness of survey data for longitudinal analyses.

Measuring spatial contexts is even more challenging than measuring school contexts, because the significant area around a family's residence, which can be considered to evoke the theoretical effects mentioned above, must be conceptualized and measured. Incorrectly operationalising spatial contexts can lead to a biased measurement of effects, the so-called modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP) (Kwan, 2012). Often, only rough administrative residential information is available such as NUTS regions or municipalities. These are too broad, particularly in cities, to reflect the segregation and community structures that matter for children's lives and families' circles of daily movements and interactions. Generating small-scale neighbourhood units requires obtaining information on families' exact residential locations. However, this information is highly sensitive, and not directly accessible for

research in many countries. While register data theoretically allows to aggregate characteristics of given neighbourhoods, survey data usually depends on official, small-scale data on neighbourhood composition from the same time periods as the survey data. This further restricts the necessary data for research.

As an additional complicating factor, contextual effects are often comparatively small. Especially when research aims to integrate multiple sources of inequality, large sample sizes are required to reliably estimate the influence of different contexts. In sum, unless large-scale surveys are available, register data are a particularly suitable option for conducting such analyses due to the large number of observations they provide. Not only do register data provide information on virtually all students within a school; they also allow researchers to track changes over time. Their scale and quality make register data highly valuable whenever they are accessible. However, they are not well suited to testing mechanisms that explain how local contexts affect educational outcomes, because this often requires observational information.

For these reasons, only few studies have empirically investigated neighbourhood effects on educational outcomes. Given these complexities, it is not surprising that research that focusses on the spatial contexts of students, families, and schools is scarce and is often limited to certain areas or cities Hillmert et al. (2023). Yet, as previously discussed, from a sociological perspective, considering all contexts is crucial, and such data and research are highly necessary.

4. Contributions

In our case studies we take a European perspective and not only restrict the analyses to a singular country but all the nine LEARN case study countries. Due to cultural, economic and social differences between countries, one might expect that educational inequalities unfold and emerge quite differently. The range of welfare regimes and educational systems in the project is impressive: The Nordic social-democratic welfare regimes Finland and Estonia have comprehensive education systems where students are tracked late. The two liberal welfare regimes Ireland and the United Kingdom come with more individualized educational choices and ability grouping. In contrast, Germany, Switzerland and the Netherlands can be characterized as conservative welfare regimes, which have implemented early between-school tracking (usually directly after primary schooling). Finally, with Italy and Romania there are two Mediterranean welfare regimes among the case studies, which provide mixed-tracking systems, where tracking starts at age 14-15 (Triventi et al., 2016; Esping-Andersen, 1990; Kääriäinen and Lehtonen, 2006). All these nine countries provide access to unique data and insights collected in

this contribution. In the following, we summarize these studies and their most important results, starting with those studies which provide evidence on school and classroom composition effects and ending with those which use spatial context data.

4.1. Effect of school and classroom composition

The **Finnish** contribution examines how individual social origin and school composition jointly influence academic success and how this relationship has evolved over the past twenty years (Gibbons et al., 2026). Using register data from 1999 to 2016, the authors compare the effects of individual social origin, measured by the highest parental occupational status (ISEI), and aggregated school-level characteristics—measured by the average occupational status of students’ parents within each school—on the probability of transitioning to the academic track after completion of comprehensive school. Accordingly, the contextual effect analysed in this study operates at the school level. Overall, the longitudinal analysis reveals a high degree of stability, with effects remaining remarkably constant over time. Both individual-level and contextual factors significantly influence the probability of transition, and their effect sizes are of similar magnitude and largely stable across the observation period, however, within-school effects being more consistent and statistically more robust. This finding indicates that even in European societies typically regarded as highly egalitarian, with comparatively low levels of inequality and highly standardized, comprehensive educational systems, both individual and school effects remain consequential. The study further shows that the proportion of high-status schools has remained relatively constant over time, suggesting that school-level segregation has not increased during the period under investigation. In addition, no interaction effects between individual social origin and school composition are detected, indicating that students do not disproportionately benefit from specific combinations of individual and contextual characteristics.

While the social context in **Estonia** is similar to Finland, a key difference lies in Estonia’s post-Soviet history (Täht et al., 2026). Against this background, it is particularly noteworthy that, despite a highly comprehensive general educational system, access to prestigious upper secondary schools is restricted, thereby generating competition. The core research questions mirror those of the Finnish study: whether individual- and context-level effects jointly contribute to academic success, how this relationship has evolved over recent decades, and whether individual and contextual effects interact. As in Finland, comprehensive register data (EHIS) are available in Estonia, enabling to observe all students over

time. Contextual effects are operationalized at the school level by aggregating information on average parental income within each school. The dependent variable captures whether a student transitions to a prestigious academic-track school after lower secondary education. The authors find that individual parental socioeconomic status—measured by education and income—is strongly predicting the transition to the academic track. However, school-level characteristics, particularly mean parental income, exert a somewhat weaker independent effect. Importantly, individual- and contextual-level effects interact positively, indicating that students from affluent families benefit most from favourable school contexts. This finding contrasts with the Finnish case, where no interaction effects were observed despite otherwise similar patterns. A further distinctive result is that, due to increasing competition and a growing student population, access to the most prestigious institutions has become more difficult over time (from 2011 to 2024). Over the course of this process, social disparities have intensified, and the likelihood of entering these tracks has increasingly favoured students from highly educated and affluent families. Overall, these findings demonstrate that even in societies formerly characterized by relatively high levels of equality, such as during the Soviet era, individual and contextual inequalities persist and appear to be widening over time.

In contrast to the previous contributions, the **Irish** case study is set in a more liberal system, where individual choices are more relevant (Heydari Barardehi et al., 2026). The authors are therefore particularly interested in the role of individual aspirations and how they shape choices and trajectories. Besides, they also take school context into account, measuring whether a school receives additional government support. Schools are only eligible for this when being located in socially disadvantaged areas. Hence, context effects are measured indirectly, yet they still capture disadvantage. While disadvantage is operationalized as a binary indicator in this study, which is rather coarse, it has the benefit of being an official indicator for general disadvantage of the school. For their study, the authors utilize various waves of the Growing Up in Ireland (GUI) panel. By doing so, they have access to individual trajectories over time. Their dependent variables are attending academic track in upper secondary education and course levels in English and mathematics. Taking a higher course level comes with educational benefits yet requires a higher level of achievement. The results show that individual factors such as parental income, educational level, and educational expectations have significant influence on these outcomes. The school context also clearly plays a role, as students in schools in disadvantaged areas face negative educational outcomes. Interestingly, these context effects are almost as large as the influence of individual parental fac-

tors. These analyses reveal that even when individual origin is taken into account, together with a large number of other controls and even parental aspirations, to be in a disadvantaged school still has a major influence on relevant educational outcomes.

In **Switzerland**, tracking starts early and is rather strict, which is rather similar to the situation in Germany [Gomenoro et al. \(2025\)](#). The authors of the case study investigate how the classroom composition influences the probability of transitioning to the general baccalaureate school (Gymnasium) in the first post-compulsory year (that is, in upper secondary education; not directly after the end of primary schooling). Classroom context factors, such as average SES, average academic performance, and the share of migrants, are supposed to be influential besides individual social origin effects. The results outline that the individual effects become smaller as soon as contexts effects are accounted for. However, the most influential predictor of the late transition is initial track placement (that happened after primary school). As soon as this variable is introduced to the models, all other effects are greatly reduced. This finding suggests earlier selection effects. Apparently, the initial track placement after primary school is largely determined by individual social origin. It appears that not unlike to the German system, Swiss schools are strong sorting machines. This result outlines that the time span when contextual effects can influence relevant outcomes is probably not very long; this window of influence also strongly depends on the educational system. It might be necessary to study earlier educational contexts (e.g. in Kindergarten) to better understand how these early context influence outcomes that happen before the major tracking points are reached. Potentially, in the Swiss case, the contextual influences (partially) determine the first transition after primary schooling but remain rather inconsequential after, since tracking explains most of the residual trajectories.

In a markedly different educational system, the **Italian** contribution examines a context in which students are required to choose an educational track after lower secondary education (Grade 8) ([Fedeli and Triventi, 2026](#)). Their study asks how peer composition effects—related both to social origin and to academic ability—influence progression to the academic track, over and above the effects of individual social origin. Owing to access to an exceptionally large register dataset covering multiple student cohorts across Italy, the study is able to identify these effects with considerable precision. The regression analyses indicate that average classroom ability exerts a negative effect on the probability of progressing to the academic track. In other words, students exposed to higher levels of competition within the classroom are less likely to transition to the academic upper secondary track. By contrast, the average social composition of the classroom has

a positive effect on this transition. In the full model, which includes all covariates, these compositional effects remain statistically significant but are attenuated when individual test scores and individual social origin are taken into account, particularly with respect to the composite social origin measure. In addition to the main analyses, the authors exploit random variation in student ability within the same schools over time to assess whether schools allocate access to upper secondary education in a fair manner, thereby strengthening the general validity of the findings. Overall, the study demonstrates that both negative and positive effects of classroom composition operate simultaneously within the Italian system, suggesting the presence of compensatory mechanisms. Nevertheless, individual social origin is a substantially stronger determinant of educational progression than compositional effects.

In **Romania**, school prestige plays a central role in educational success, as students actively seek admission to schools with strong reputations ([Dodan et al., 2025](#)). In this contribution, the authors first trace the development of pupils' academic performance over time and classify students into three latent performance trajectories. Having operationalized this key predictor of educational success, they then examine how these trajectories influence performance in the final school-leaving examination (the Baccalaureate). The results show that placement in the academic track and the prestige of the school (based on admission rates and grades) substantially shape performance trajectories, whereas parental educational attainment contributes relatively little once these contextual factors are taken into account. Due to data limitations, the direct effects of contextual variables on performance in the final examination cannot be assessed. However, their influence on earlier ability trajectories is clearly demonstrated. As observed in other national contexts (e.g., Switzerland), initial track placement appears to be decisive, while subsequent contextual influences are of comparatively lesser importance. Taken together, the Romanian study underscores the importance of examining early educational contexts to understand how early selection shapes later educational outcomes.

4.2. Effects of neighbourhood contexts

Similar to the Irish case, the contribution from the **United Kingdom** deals with a rather liberal system that is determined by free individual choices ([Kelly et al., 2026](#)). Yet even these traditional liberal systems appear to become more regulated as reforms show. This contribution investigates how individual social origin and social context together influence educational decisions and outcomes of students and how this relates to educational inequality. For this aim it combines three large-scale panel surveys (MCS, COSMO, and Next Steps) in order to compare cohorts. Furthermore, it includes a large amount

of information on the family situation as well as on contexts. These are operationalized by measuring the share of children in a rather small geographical area that are considered income deprived. The outcome variables measure whether a student attends the academic track in upper secondary education or selects an academic profile that supports further educational progress (two facilitating A-level courses). While there is clear evidence that socially disadvantaged students face worse educational outcomes, as they obtain the A-level degree less often and also do not select a demanding A-level course profile as often as advantaged students, the context effects are much smaller and often not statistically significant in the full models. In some models of some cohorts, clear negative effects of deprived contexts remain. Given the large sample size and the various datasets and cohorts used, these results can be regarded as robust.

In **Germany**, tracking starts early, which is rather similar to the situation in Switzerland, and determines strongly educational attainment and later life chances of students. The German study thus focusses on the transition from primary to tracked secondary education, taking into account parental idealistic and realistic educational aspirations, teachers' school recommendations and the school track entered in secondary school (Bittmann and Kleinert, 2026). The study asks how neighbourhood composition, school composition and family backgrounds jointly affect this transition process. The contribution combines longitudinal survey data from a large-scale panel study among primary school students (NEPS-SC2) with small-scale spatial data. Firstly, the results show that all indicators of neighbourhood composition (poverty, educational composition, and share of non-Germans), school composition (educational background, migration background) and family backgrounds (social origin, migration background) are systematically associated with each other, suggesting a considerable amount of residential segregation, which is reflected in school composition. Second, while some neighbourhood effects on aspirations and transitions can be detected when they are introduced solely, they disappear as soon as school context and family backgrounds are accounted for. In contrast, school composition does still matter in the full models, indicating that students in schools with higher shares of academically educated parents tend to have better outcomes, on average. The same is true for students in schools with higher shares of immigrant background students, when student differences in competences are controlled for. The most important factor influencing transition outcomes, however, is individual family backgrounds, in particular, social origin. Importantly, a disadvantaged social and migration background and the respective school contexts often go along with each other, but have opposite effects on the chances to enter the Gymnasium, the higher secondary school track.

While the educational system in the **Netherlands** is similar to the German or Swiss one, however, students are sorted later and into a higher number of tracks (Zwier et al., 2026). By leveraging extremely detailed spatial data that is combined with register data, the Dutch contribution (authors) investigates two main research questions: first, whether socially advantaged families move to 'good' neighbourhoods before schooling starts and second, how individual factors, neighbourhoods, and school contexts influence school success. The dependent variable measures whether the student receives a recommendation for the academic track (pre-university). The first finding is that socially advantaged families are more likely than others to move to neighbourhoods with high reputation schools before their children enter school, which demonstrates social self-selection into favourable conditions. Secondly, they report that school quality (measured by the share of students receiving a pre-university track recommendation) and neighbourhood SES influence educational outcomes positively, yet individual factors such as parental education and income weigh larger. This is the only contribution that can show that parents are aware of the quality of schools and attempt to get access to good schools even before their children make the transition. Hence, this contribution offers an important explanation for the tight interrelation of neighbourhood context and individual social background: self-selection. There is no reason to believe that this mechanism is unique to the Netherlands.

5. Conclusions

In this collection of studies, we are able to provide new insights on how contextual effects contribute to educational inequalities for many European countries. The available data sources are impressive and include not only long-running panel studies, but also provide access to various other sources. Some countries can leverage register data (such as Finland and Estonia), others have access to detailed neighbourhood data, such as Germany and the Netherlands. Most studies provide information about school and classroom contexts, which is also an established way, as classrooms are the place where student spend most of their time to learn and develop. Given the broad variation of data and statistical approaches, it is interesting to see that across the nine European case studies, a number of highly consistent findings and general conclusions emerge, despite substantial institutional, cultural, and historical differences between welfare regimes and educational systems.

First, even when educational and/or neighbourhood composition is taken into account, individual social origin is a strong and persistent predictor of educational outcomes in all countries examined. Parental education, income, and

occupational status systematically shape students' transitions into academic tracks, course levels, and examination success. This holds across comprehensive systems with late tracking (e.g. Finland, Estonia), mixed systems (e.g. Italy, Romania), and highly stratified systems with early tracking (e.g. Switzerland, Germany, the Netherlands). Even where contextual effects are present, individual-level socioeconomic characteristics typically exert the largest influence. School, classroom, and neighbourhood contexts matter as well, but their effects are generally secondary to individual social origin and are highly dependent on institutional settings. School- and classroom-level composition effects are nearly consistently detected across countries, indicating that students' outcomes are influenced by the socioeconomic and academic characteristics of peers in their schools. However, these effects are often modest and frequently attenuated once individual background and prior achievement are taken into account. In several cases, such as Germany, Switzerland and the United Kingdom, context effects become very small or statistically insignificant once family backgrounds are controlled for.

Furthermore, early selection and tracking strongly condition the scope for contextual effects. In systems with early and rigid tracking (e.g. Switzerland, Romania), initial track placement largely determines later educational trajectories, leaving limited room for subsequent school or classroom contexts to alter outcomes. These systems function as strong sorting mechanisms, with social inequalities being largely locked in at early educational stages.

What also has been shown by the studies is the complex interplay between various layers of students' social contexts. While individual families are nested within geographical neighbourhoods, schools and classrooms form another level that is not necessarily (but often) serving the same neighbourhood. As students can belong to multiple contexts at the same time (for example, meeting one peer group in school while meeting another in their leisure time), another layer of complexity in social interaction is added. While no single study can investigate all these effects at the same time, taken together, the synthesis of all contributions outlines how various aspects can influence educational success. They show that interactions between individual background and context are generally weak or absent, but where they do appear, they tend to reinforce inequality. Most studies find no strong interaction effects, suggesting that students do not systematically benefit from particular combinations of individual and contextual characteristics. An important exception is Estonia, where advantaged students benefit disproportionately from favourable school contexts, indicating cumulative advantage rather than compensation. On another level, the Italian results show that even the same context may evoke contrasting effects on single students.

In sum, these results suggest that it is quite difficult to overcome individual social disadvantages as even good schools or affluent neighbourhoods will not easily compensate for these. Of course, such "mismatches" between individual origin and contexts are rare; they do occur, but in most cases families apparently self-select into areas with similar social standing as they have. The Dutch contribution delivers strong empirical evidence for this assumption. The results show that high-status families attempt to find "better" neighbourhoods before children enter schooling.

All in all, this collection of articles provides an overview of the most-recent research on the interplay between educational success and various local contexts across Europe. By compiling this information, the project LEARN adds new insights that go beyond previous research. Despite these knowledge gains, there are still many open questions regarding the effects of learning and living environments of children in European context. Most importantly, we do not know how comparable the findings from single countries are across Europe, e.g. the positive effect of social school and classroom composition and the negative effect of ability composition on single students, the self-selection of advantaged families into neighbourhoods with high-quality schools, or the negative effects of disadvantaged local contexts for school success. To answer these questions and to compare European countries more directly would require a system of harmonized large-scale educational register data, because only these data sources offer the completeness and statistical power to detect effects of local contexts and their complex interrelation among each other and with individual characteristics on individual educational success.

6. Policy implications

Based on the empirical evidence synthesized in this summary, several policy implications can be derived. First, policies should place a strong emphasis on early intervention and prevention. Since individual social origin exerts a strong and persistent influence on educational trajectories—and since early selection mechanisms tend to lock in inequalities—support for disadvantaged children must begin well before major tracking decisions are made. High-quality early childhood education and care, targeted language support, and early diagnostic and remedial measures are crucial to reduce disparities before they become institutionalized within school systems. Evidence from countries with early tracking suggests that once initial placements are made, later school or classroom contexts have limited capacity to compensate for early disadvantages. Family-oriented policies are essential complements to tackle educational inequalities by social origin. Given the central role of parental education, income, and resources, ed-

educational inequality cannot be effectively addressed without supporting disadvantaged families more broadly. Parental guidance and counselling—particularly with respect to educational pathways and transitions—may help reduce informational asymmetries that disproportionately disadvantage lower-status families.

Additional resources should be systematically directed toward disadvantaged schools and educational contexts. Although contextual effects are generally smaller than individual background effects, studies from various countries show that students in schools in socioeconomically disadvantaged environments show on average poorer educational achievement. Furthermore, the results in this volume suggest that individual students benefit from being in socially advantageous schools. Targeted funding, additional support staff, and enhanced pedagogical resources can help mitigate these disadvantages. Importantly, such measures should be sustained and structural rather than short-term, as isolated interventions are unlikely to offset deeply rooted inequalities.

Finally, policies aimed at reducing segregation between schools and neighbourhoods deserve renewed attention. The evidence of strong self-selection by advantaged families into high-status neighbourhoods and schools—most clearly demonstrated in the Dutch case—suggests that educational inequality emerges even before formal schooling begins and is reinforced over time by being exposed to schools and neighbourhoods that resemble one's own family background. Desegregation policies, such as spreading social housing over different areas or providing other incentives for social mixing may help weaken the tight link between family background, residential location, and school quality. While such policies are politically sensitive, the findings indicate that without addressing residential segregation, contextual inequalities will persist.

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